

Glenna2 Nordic Cloud

Aim3 Target 4 Kubeflow Evaluation

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Abstract

Kubeflow is a Google-backed project that aims to provide a curated collection of existing state-of-art machine learning tools compatible with Kubernetes environments all in a single package, in addition to some services created by Kubeflow. With a large foothold in the cloud computing scene, Kubernetes is widely adopted as the industry standard and with this in mind Kubeflow looks like a promising option for working with machine learning in this scene.

Part of the goals within the Glenna2 project is providing cloud-based tools and infrastructure for researchers in the Nordics to use for their work. With the increasing trend of applying machine learning to various problems, utilizing the cloud for these workloads provides an appealing alternative for large-scale computations.

Given the opportunities Kubeflow suggests, the Glenna2 project decided to take a closer look and evaluate Kubeflow. The major effort in this evaluation was focused on KfPipelines.

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From	Oliver Stein	SNIC/UU	Nov 2019
Reviewed by	Michaela Barth	NeIC	Dec 2019
Approved by	Glenna2 Steering Group	NeIC	Dec 31 2019

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Glenna2 - Kubeflow evaluation

The following is the report of Glenna2 Aim 3: Target 4, covering the following topics:

1. Introduction to Kubeflow
2. Setting up the framework
3. Machine learning workflow example
4. Evaluating the experience of using Kubeflow
5. Conclusion and ideas for further work

The report is written by Oliver Stein

1 Introduction to Kubeflow

Part of the goals within the Glenna2 project is providing cloud-based tools and infrastructure for researchers in the Nordics to use for their work. With the increasing trend of applying machine learning to various problems, utilizing the cloud for these workloads provides an appealing alternative for large-scale computations.

Kubeflow is a Google-backed project that aims to provide a curated collection of existing state-of-art machine learning tools compatible with *Kubernetes* environments all in a single package, in addition to some services created by Kubeflow. With a large foothold in the cloud computing scene, *Kubernetes* is widely adopted as the industry standard and with this in mind Kubeflow looks like a promising option for working with machine learning in this scene.

The project is currently under active development and is open-source, publishing the source code under the Kubeflow GitHub organization¹. It is still not at a stage of full release, but stable versions of the current tools and setup are continuously released as development progresses.

¹<https://github.com/kubeflow>

Figure 1: The Kubeflow central dashboard UI.

1.1 What is included

As Kubeflow evolves, additional components and tools are added to the project continuously. The currently available components are always listed in the documentation², although some of them might need further installation or setup and do not come “out of the box”. Some of the tools are developed by the Kubeflow team, including a central dashboard panel to access and interact the Kubeflow deployment (see fig. 1).

Other than the dashboard, the project provides a workflow engine called *Kubeflow Pipelines* (or KfPipelines, KfP) based on the Kubernetes-native Argo workflow engine. The workflow engine allows users to construct simple or complex pipelines, and while mainly intended to create machine learning pipelines, KfPipelines is capable of performing a variety of other workflow tasks.

Kubeflow also provides a service for hosting and running *Jupyter Notebooks*, which can be customized in terms of computing resources available, custom storage from Kubernetes volumes and such. The notebooks are configured and accessed from the Kubeflow dashboard.

Furthermore, there is a growing collection of tools for doing **training** and **servng** of machine learning models. It spans mostly preexisting tools and frameworks from the industry that have been adapted for running in Kubeflow, simplifying the process of running some of these tools in a cloud environment. As of version 0.6.2, the following components are included:

²<https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/components/>

Training Kubeflow provides a custom Job resource for a variety of frameworks that can be used for training machine learning models, namely *TensorFlow*, *PyTorch*, *MXNet*, *Chainer* and *MPI*. These jobs can be created and directly deployed in the Kubernetes cluster and are scheduled and managed automatically.

Serving For serving machine learning models for online prediction, Kubeflow supports several options including multiple formats of *TensorFlow Serving* and additionally *Seldon* for serving any model that is supported in the Seldon project documentation³.

2 Deploying Kubeflow

All the details for getting started with Kubeflow are documented⁴, and in addition archived details related to previous versions are also kept available. As of writing this report, the latest released version of Kubeflow is 0.7.0 (released November 4th 2019), but the work during the evaluation has mainly targeted versions **0.6.0** through **0.6.2**.

As described in the documentation, Kubeflow is meant to support public cloud environments, existing Kubernetes clusters and Linux, MacOS and Windows servers/workstations. To facilitate the installation of Kubeflow, a command line tool called *kfctl* is provided. This tool uses a yaml configuration file as a baseline, which specifies what components of Kubeflow to install and the source of configurations for all these components. The main configuration files are provided on GitHub (here version 0.6.2 was used⁵), with different branches containing various installation configurations for each released version.

With *kfctl* (tool version 0.6.2), the simplified process of deploying Kubeflow is as follows:

Initialize a directory for the Kubeflow application:

```
kfctl init -V --<directory name> \  
--config=<url or path to configuration yaml>
```

Inside the new directory, generate all Kubernetes resources:

```
kfctl generate all -V
```

Modify any of the generated Kubernetes resources as desired and apply them:

```
kfctl apply all -V
```

This results in all the components of Kubeflow being deployed in the Kubernetes cluster according to the configurations of the resources.

³<https://docs.seldon.io/projects/seldon-core/en/latest/wrappers/README.html>

⁴<https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/started/getting-started/>

⁵<https://github.com/kubeflow/kubeflow/tree/v0.6.2/bootstrap/config>

2.1 Notes about installation

In the current state, there are some caveats to note for the installation process. Most important is that when initializing a new directory, this directory must not already exist. This means that it will not be possible to regenerate all the resources from the original Kubeflow configurations for an existing project, and directly updating existing projects becomes a more complex process. This is also reflected in the documentation⁶, stating that Kubeflow will not officially support backwards compatibility and upgradability until the project releases version 1.0.

Another important observation is that Kubeflow relies on a project called Istio⁷ for handling ingress (access from external sources) and service routing among other things. While this component is installed by default in several of the configurations provided, in particular for the on-premises Kubernetes installation, the component can be also installed manually in the cluster and omitted from the Kubeflow configuration. This is useful since Istio can interact with a cluster across namespaces in unexpected ways, and care should be taken to configure it properly. With Istio in place, Kubeflow deploys an ingress rule through which the central dashboard of Kubeflow is accessed.

3 Example of Kubeflow Pipelines workflow

The major effort in this investigation was focused on KfPipelines. For this, a workflow was developed using the tool in which a machine learning model is trained and packaged into a container for serving predictions. The source code of this example is available on GitHub⁸, along with more detailed documentation and instructions for running it.

The workflow consists of 4 stages; data preprocessing, training the model, evaluating the model and finally packaging the model into a Docker container. This workflow was adapted from a set of Python scripts running through the entire process. Keeping the original code mostly as-is, each part is run via a main shell script within each pipeline stage. A Docker container was created for each individual pipeline stage, including the shell script for that stage, the source code for the Python scripts and any other dependencies. These containers are also available in the GitHub repository. Figure 2 illustrates the graph of the workflow.

One addition to the original machine learning code was to take the resulting models and package them in an OpenFaaS-based Docker container, which can be deployed on an OpenFaaS server and from there serve predictions from a web endpoint. OpenFaaS is currently not a native component of Kubeflow, but the choice of how to serve models is arbitrary and this aligned with the available environment during the evaluation process.

Additionally, in order to test the pipeline parameters feature, the workflow includes a

⁶<https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/upgrading/upgrade/>

⁷<https://istio.io/>

⁸https://github.com/pharmbio/kubeflow-pipelines/tree/master/kensert_CNN

Figure 2: The graph describing the example pipeline in the Kubeflow UI, showing the four steps in the pipeline.

set of parameters that can be set when starting a run. One of the features to parameterize was whether to “checkpoint” a workflow step, i.e. skipping the calculations of that step and using the stored intermediary results so as to save time. Other parameters include the endpoint to the Docker registry for uploading the packaged model container, the directory name for all intermediary results in the storage backend and a dummy training parameter for demonstration. Figure 3 illustrates how the parameters are displayed when starting a pipeline execution run.

4 Evaluation of working with Kubeflow

During the investigation, a subset of the components and aspects of Kubeflow have been tested; as mentioned above KfPipelines has been the main focus of the evalua-

Run Type

One-off Recurring

Run parameters

Specify parameters required by the pipeline

model-type	Inception_v3
artifact-bucket	kensert_CNN
checkpoint-preprocess	false
checkpoint-training	false
checkpoint-evaluation	false
workspace-name	kensert_CNN
model-repo	

Figure 3: The parameters available for a pipeline that can be entered when starting a run in the Kubeflow pipeline UI.

tion. Furthermore, the Jupyter Notebook server was also briefly investigated, and the entire process of installing and managing Kubeflow in a Kubernetes cluster as well as version control for the installation was also a large part of the investigation.

In addition to this, the portability of working with Kubeflow was also tested. To test this, a Kubernetes cluster was installed on resources provided by the CSC community cloud cPouta, and Kubeflow was installed in this cluster. The goal of the test was to determine whether a pipeline developed for one cluster can be run “as-is” in a different cluster with Kubeflow deployed.

Again, as stated previously, Kubeflow is continuously evolving and the verdict is based on the results and experience from a specific version in the early stages of the framework. With this in mind, the process of deploying Kubeflow has notably changed even during the investigation, and may change further after this report is finalized. The same is true for the what components are available and compatible with Kubeflow.

4.1 Kubeflow Pipelines

Working with KfPipelines has provided some insight into the potential of the workflow system. Based on the example implemented above, KfPipelines looks like a compelling alternative for designing complex machine learning workflows, especially with regards to the flexibility and freedom in how to design the workflow steps.

In addition to the flexibility, the Kubeflow dashboard provides a GUI with which to upload pipelines and start, monitor and interact with pipeline runs e. g. showing the output of pods running the pipeline steps. The interface is arguably simple to navigate and has provided access to all relevant features while working with the example pipeline used in this evaluation. See figs. 4 and 5 for more examples of the UI components.

Figure 4: The overview of the available pipelines in the Kubeflow UI.

While the tool provides flexibility, it also comes with a requirement of understanding Kubernetes and the underlying architecture to a significant degree. Writing a pipeline definition is done in Python. Defining the pipeline stages includes declaring Kubernetes resources like the amount of CPUs, RAM etc., any secrets needed for e. g. Docker or Git credentials, underlying storage like volume claims and so on. This may be outside the scope of the “average data scientist” and while there are examples and documentation available these are not necessarily easy to adapt to the cluster that a user is working in. Furthermore, restructuring a training script to run in steps as Docker containers may also be a complicated step for the user. Thus there is a potentially steep learning curve.

Since the workflow is defined programmatically, however, it is also possible to tem-

Figure 5: Starting a run by choosing what pipeline to run and what experiment to associate it with in the Kubeflow UI.

platize and define helper functions for someone with the Kubernetes know-how. This could greatly reduce the learning curve and allow data scientists to focus on designing the workflows at a higher level. Naturally, this depends on the knowledgebase in a team and how that team operates.

Another drawback to KfPipelines is that currently it is not possible to define some resources as pipeline parameters, most notably CPU, RAM, GPU etc. This leads to having to know the resource requirements in advance when building a pipeline, and having to rebuild the pipeline if for example the typical workload varies for various inputs. This may lead to overcommitting resources and/or repeating and duplicating pipelines. The issue is intrinsic to the underlying Argo workflow engine, and recently a fix has been proposed⁹ but not yet adapted for Kubeflow.

It is also worth noting that persisting the logs of pipeline containers is not supported officially, in the sense that the logs are only maintained for as long as the Kubernetes pods remain in the system. For instance, if a user cleans up completed workflows this results in losing the logs associated with these. This is also a known issue¹⁰, but as of yet it seems to not have a final solution. Figure 6 shows how the logs are currently accessible from the Kubeflow UI.

⁹<https://github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/issues/1252>

¹⁰<https://github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/issues/844>

Figure 6: The logs from one of the steps in the example pipeline shown in the Kubeflow UI.

With regards to the portability of the pipelines the previously described test was successful. This indicates that pipelines are indeed portable between Kubeflow environments. After setting up a Kubernetes environment and deploying Kubeflow, the same pipeline example that was developed during the investigation on local resources was tested. Following the instructions available on the GitHub repository for running the pipeline, it was successfully executed.

4.2 Notebook server

Besides the KfPipelines component, Kubeflow’s Jupyter Notebook server was investigated as well. As mentioned, the notebook server provides a central interface to list, create, manage and access Jupyter notebooks. Additionally, Kubeflow features user profiles that provide namespace isolation between each profile’s collection of notebooks, reducing the risk of accidental modification or removal of other notebooks without completely isolating them.

The process of creating and accessing notebooks through the interface was in general simple and intuitive. Using the Docker images provided by Kubeflow together with automated creation of new Kubernetes volumes for storage worked without issues which allows for quick and easy setup of notebook environments for users. A notable caveat is that if a user wants to start a notebook with GPU access (provided the cluster has access to this) the option to do so is not clear from the instructions in the interface.

Since using GPUs is a common practice when working with machine learning, this should be more clear; currently a user has to specify `{"nvidia.com/gpu":1}` in the “Extra Resources” field to add 1 GPU.

However, there were some issues when trying to run more customized setups. Running notebooks with user-submitted Docker images was not successful during the tests, but there is documentation on how to achieve this. Additionally, it should be possible to use existing Kubernetes volumes for both the notebook workspace and additional data volumes, but all attempts at adding these were unsuccessful. Based on the tests, extra care with reading and writing permissions on the volumes’ filesystems is needed to make them cooperate with Kubeflow’s notebook server. On paper however, this is a great feature for providing access to additional datasets outside the notebook which may readily be available in the cluster.

4.3 Installing and managing Kubeflow

This evaluation was based on deploying Kubeflow in a Kubernetes cluster, in particular running in an on-premises set of server VMs. As such, the installation followed the documentation for this scenario.

The most notable observation was that when generating the Kubernetes configurations for all components to install, a lot of these are not namespaced, meaning that simple removal of a Kubeflow deployment by removing related namespaces in the cluster is not supported. Instead, completely purging a cluster of any Kubeflow-related resources requires a more involved approach of tracking down all traces, manually removing them. This has led to an issue on the GitHub repository raising awareness of the problem¹¹. It is as of yet still a tedious process that interferes frequently while setting up Kubeflow initially or when reinstalling or updating to newer versions.

Another issue is the dependency on the Istio framework, which adds further complexity to the setup. Istio is a large and complex framework with an abundance of features, and might incur a large overhead in terms of installation complexity. The main caveat is understanding how to reconfigure the default installation of Istio that is optionally included with Kubeflow, or installing it manually, in such a way that it does not interfere with other areas of the cluster. As an example, installing Istio with the default configuration caused the creation of Kubernetes secrets for services across the entire cluster intended for enabling Istio side-car injection, a feature intended to allow service traffic to be managed by Istio. This was not documented in the instructions, and there may be other side-effects that are unwanted when installing Istio with the default configuration. On the other hand, this provides an opportunity to take advantage of the features provided by Istio should the user wish to do so. As an alternative, deploying a minimal Istio installation is a less complicated task than modifying the provided configuration, and in doing so it is possible to configure the features of Istio with more control.

As for version controlling the installation, this can be done but there are some more

¹¹<https://github.com/kubeflow/kubeflow/issues/3767>

caveats to keep in mind. As mentioned in the section on installing Kubeflow, the configuration files are generated by `kfctl` into a directory and tracking this folder with e. g. Git can allow for keeping a version history of the Kubeflow setup. The major issue with this approach is that if a user modifies these generated configurations, it is hard to keep these changes in case of re-generating the setup, for example when upgrading to a new Kubeflow release. A potential solution is to maintain each setup version in separate folders, i.e. initializing a new repository each time with `kfctl`. As the Kubeflow project matures this is likely to improve and stabilize with subsequent versions. Until that point, upgrading Kubeflow and porting customizations while keeping track of any modifications will require some effort.

5 Conclusion and future ideas

To conclude, based on this investigation Kubeflow looks to be an interesting candidate approach for centralizing machine learning operations in Kubernetes environments, or at least parts of the operations. The investigation has touched upon a limited set of the features of the framework and the verdict is only reflecting these features. The project is under active development as can be seen on the GitHub organization with support for features coming from both the project developers and the community. Kubeflow is targeted for a production grade 1.0 release in January 2020. The release will contain a core set of applications targeting the user journey of 'build-train-deploy' and scaffolding to deploy and manage multi-user Kubeflow environments on-premise and in the cloud.

Despite some issues with or lack of certain features, the framework provides a solid tool with Kubeflow Pipelines for building workflows and a promising start for a notebook server that can simplify the process of setting up notebook environments for data scientists.

As discussed, there is potentially a steeper learning curve for some of the target user groups. Users with a data scientist background or similar may lack proficiency with Kubernetes concepts that are required to build workflows with `KfPipelines` or even setting up notebooks with GPUs or external datasets. Much of this is due to lack of or unclear documentation for Kubeflow. This is likely to improve over time. As things stand currently, using this framework will likely require teams or personnel with experience in Kubernetes to make good use of Kubeflow's features.

5.1 Further investigation and ideas

While the exploration of Kubeflow has mainly touched upon the subjects discussed so far, some effort has been put into what should be further investigated to address issues or explore other useful features.

One of the main struggles in this area seems to be how to transfer machine learning from exploratory and testing environments like notebooks and loose scripts into repeatable, scalable workflows. One potential tool to help this process is Kubeflow

Fairing¹², which is intended to aid the user with training and deploying machine learning models in Kubeflow. Another common objective is hyperparameter tuning machine learning problems, for which the tool Katib¹³ is intended.

Additionally, tools included in the Kubeflow framework for model serving are also potential targets for further testing, like Seldon and the new KfServing component developed by Kubeflow. It may also be interesting to investigate the training jobs that are supported and compare how working with these compares to running the entire process in a pipeline, and even whether all of these components can be combined.

¹²<https://github.com/kubeflow/fairing>

¹³<https://github.com/kubeflow/katib>